

Integrated germplasm improvement–upland

Makiling, an improved variety for acid upland areas in the Philippines

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The Philippine Seed Board recently approved the release of breeding line IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 as PSBRC-1, popular name Makiling, for planting in acid upland areas. This cultivar was derived from KN-1B-361-1-8-6//E425/IR22///BPI-76*9/Dawn, using parents from Indonesia, West Africa, Philippines, and the U.S.

KN-1B-361-1-8-6 and E425 are sources of drought resistance and tolerance for acid soils. E425 is also resistant to blast and has a deep and thick root system. Recovery ability after

moisture stress is contributed by the BPI-76*9/Dawn parent. Good eating quality is contributed by parents from Indonesia and the Philippines.

Makiling has a green basal leaf sheath. The flag leaf angle is intermediate. Under favorable conditions, panicle length is about 25 cm. The flag leaf is about 35 cm long. The lemma and palea have gold furrows on a straw background and short hairs at the upper portion. The gold color is more intense in the upper portion of the panicles, fading toward the base. Apiculus color is straw and the grains have no awns. Grain shape is intermediately slender.

Data from the National Rice Cooperative Testing Project (NRCT) of the Rice Varietal Improvement Group of the Philippine Seed Board showed that Makiling varies in plant height, from 94 to 130 cm, and matures in 114-130 d,

depending on location and environmental conditions.

It is resistant to deadhearts and moderately resistant to whiteheads caused by the striped stem borer. It is moderately susceptible to the yellow stem borer and three races of brown planthopper. It is resistant to blast, and has intermediate resistance to bacterial blight, ragged stunt, and grassy stunt virus.

Amylose content is about 20% and gel consistency is 48%. Head rice recovery is 48%; milling recovery averages 64%, with 4.5% chalky grains.

In field tests at IRRRI, Makiling showed moderate resistance to field drought and good recovery ability.

In six regional trials in the Philippines, Makiling yielded an average 2.4 t/ha over four seasons (Table 1), 4% higher than the check. In farmer-managed NRCT trials over three seasons, the yield advantage was 6% (Table 2). In regional trials, Makiling performed best in Tupi, South Cotabato, and Musuan, Bukidnon, where the soil is acid. In on-farm trials, it performed best in Calaca, Batangas, and Janiuay, Iloilo. ■

Table 1. Yield over locations^a and seasons of promising upland rice selection IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 and check UPLRi-5, National Rice Cooperative Testing Project, Philippine Seed Board, 1985-88.^b

Year, season	Yield (t/ha)						Season mean (t/ha)
	CMU	IES	LGES	MRRTC	UPLB	TSF	
	<i>UPLRi-5 (check)</i>						
1985 WS	4.0	3.4			2.5	2.4	3.1
1986 WS	1.9	2.2		2.3		3.4	2.5
1987 WS	3.0		1.2			2.8	2.3
1988 WS	3.6	2.1	1.5	1.0	2.4		"1
	<i>IR10147-113-5-1-1-5</i>						
1985	3.7	2.8			2.2	3.4	3.0
1986	3.9	1.8	-2.0	0	2.5	2.5	
1987	3.5		1.3			3.1	2.6
1988	2.3	1.1	1.5	1.2	2.1		1.6
	GMTE = 2.4	GMC = 2.5	YA = -3.9%	No.* = 3/16	No.# = 3/16		

^aCMU = Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, IES = Ilagan Experimental Station, Isabela, LGES = La Granja Experimental Station, Negros Occidental, MRRTC = Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, UPLB = University of the Philippines at Los Baños, College, Laguna, TSF = Tupi Seed Farm, South Cotabato. ^bGMTE = grand mean of test entry; GMC = grand mean of check YA = yield advantage of a given test entry over the check [(GMTE - GMC) + GMC] × 100, No. * = number of time a test entry has significantly higher yield than the check. No. # = lower than the check.

Table 2. Grain yield of promising upland rice selections in on-farm trials, National Rice Cooperative Testing Project, Philippine Seed Board, 1987-89 wet season.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	UPLRi-5 (Check)			IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 (PSBRi 3)		
	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989
Trece Martires, Cavite		1.0	4.8		1.1	4.2
Calaca, Batangas	4.3	2.2	3.3	4.3	2.6	4.0
Padre Garcia, Batangas	4.7			4.5		
Janiuay, Iloilo #1		3.5			3.7	
Maasin, South Leyte	2.7			2.9		
Janiuay, Iloilo #2	-	3.6			4.7	
Victorias, Negros		2.2	1.7		1.9	2.1
Mean	3.9	2.5	3.2	3.9	2.8	3.4

Integrated germplasm improvement–rainfed

TP-AS42673, a high-yielding, short-duration rice for semidry and wet conditions

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In Agasteeswaram and Thoivalai Taluks of Kanyakumari district, 7,000 ha of rice is direct seeded in semidry conditions during May when the summer rains start. It grows 40-50 d with available soil moisture, then is converted to wet conditions when canal water is received for irrigation. In 7,000 ha of transplanted rice, nurseries are raised Jun-Jul after receipt of canal water.

We evaluated eight improved short-duration cultures under both conditions 1989-91, with popular varieties TPS1 and TKM9 as checks. Test plots were 5 × 4 m,

laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Three seeds/hill were dibbled in May at 15- × 10-cm row spacing for semidry conditions and three seedling/hill were transplanted in July at 15- × 10-cm spacing for wet conditions. Fertilizer was applied at 75-37.5-37.5 kg NPK/ha.

TP-AS42673 (ASD/IR36) gave the highest mean grain yield under both conditions (see table). Its higher yield potential may be ascribed to more productive tillers and more grains/panicle.

TP-AS42673 is a semidwarf variety with high tillering ability and light green foliage. The panicle is compact with good spikelet fertility. Grain is short bold, with a white pericarp. It shows tolerance for drought and blast. ■

Performance of TP-AS42673 under semidry and wet conditions at Agricultural Research Station, Thirupathisaram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)						Overall mean	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)
		Semidry			Wet					
		1989	1990	Mean	1989	1990	Mean			
TP-AS42673	ASD8/IR36	4.6	4.7	4.6	5.0	4.6	4.8	4.7	10	202
TP-AS26556	IET5233/IR2153	5.3	4.5	4.9	2.9	3.8	3.3	4.1	10	179
TP-AS22954	IRON309/ADT31	4.9	4.2	4.5	3.8	3.9	3.8	4.1	10	188
TP-AS42700	ASD8/IR50	4.2	4.1	4.1	4.2	4.0	4.1	4.1	8	178
TP-AS25370	ASD1/IRON297	2.8	3.9	3.3	4.6	4.5	4.5	4.0	7	174
TP-AS42698	ASD8/IR36	4.4	3.5	3.9	3.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	8	152
TP-AS42692	ASD8/IR36	4.3	3.2	3.7	3.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	9	149
TP-AS37419	IET1444/IR20	3.8	3.3	3.5	4.0	3.1	3.5	3.6	7	128
TPS1 (check)	IR8/Kattisamba	5.1	4.1	4.6	3.6	3.9	3.7	4.1	8	178
TKM9 (check)	TKM7/IR8	4.2	3.5	3.8	3.3	4.2	3.7	3.6	8	162
	LSD (0.05)	1.1	0.2	0.7	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5		

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

Newly released deepwater rice varieties in West Bengal

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Four new rice varieties developed for deep water (50-100 cm) at the Chinsurah RRS were released in 1989.

NC490 (IET8987), released as Nalini, is a pureline selection from farmers' cultivar Sindurmukhi. It is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers 26-28 Oct in West Bengal. Well-exserted panicles are 22 cm long with about 200 medium slender grains (5.6 mm long, 2.5 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 20 g. Highest yield was 5.8 t/ha at Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, in 1983 preliminary yield trials. Average yield was 3.4 t/ha (see table). Nalini is resistant to blast (Bl) and moderately resistant to stem borer (SB), sheath blight (ShB), and bacterial blight (BB).

NC491 (IET8988), released as Matangini, was selected from Kajallata. It flowers in late Oct. Its compact panicle has about 200 short bold grains (6 mm long, 2.0 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 27.2 g. It had the highest yield at CRRI, 6.6 t/ha in 1983. Matangini is

Yields of new deepwater rice varieties in state and national trials in India, 1983-88.

Year	Trial ^a	Sites (no.)	Water depth (cm)	Yield ^b (t/ha)	
				New variety	Check
<i>NC490 (IET8987), Nalini</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	7	42 - 75	3.6*	2.9 (Tilakkachari)
1984	National (UVT-5)	7	36 - 66	3.1	2.8 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	10	22 - 90	3.0**	1.9 (Janki)
1985	Physiological screening	3		3.5*	2.8 (Local variety)
1986-88	State adaptive	4	50 - 85	3.1*	2.5 (Tilakkachari)
1988	On-farm (minikit) (3 districts)	8		3.9	
	Total or av	36		3.4	
<i>NC491 (IET8988), Matangini</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	3	42 - 65	3.8**	2.3 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	9	22 - 90	3.0	2.7 (Local variety)
1985	Physiological screening	1		2.5	2.2 (Local variety)
1986	National (UVT-5)	3	62 - 110	2.5	2.1 (Local variety)
1986	Physiological screening	2		3.3*	2.8 (Local variety)
1986-88	State adaptive	5	65-100	3.4*	2.6 (NC487)
	Total or ave	23		3.1	
<i>NC493 (IET8989), Amulya</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	4	42 - 75	3.3	2.9 (Tilakkachari)
1984	National (UVT-5)	8	36 - 66	3.1*	2.5 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	9	22 - 90	3.2**	2.0 (Janki)
1985	Physiological screening	4		3.6	3.2 (Local variety)
1987-88	State adaptive	2	55 - 95	3.0*	2.2 (NC488)
1988	On-farm (minikit) (3 districts)	8		3.1	
	Total or av	35		3.2	
<i>CN570-652-39-2 (IET10001), Dinesh</i>					
1985	National (PVT-5)	3	40 - 55	3.3*	2.7 (Tilakkachari)
1986	National (UVT-5)	4			1.9 (Local variety)
1986	Physiological screening	2	62 - 113	2.7*	1.9 (Janki)
1987	National (UVT-5)	5	50 - 108	4.5**	2.8 (Local variety)
				3.0*	2.2 (Local variety)
1987-88	National (UVT-6)	3	95 - 116	3.5**	2.4 (Local variety)
1987	Physiological screening	1		3.5	3.0 (NC492)
1987-88	State adaptive	2	75 - 105	3.3**	2.1 (Jaladhi 2)
	Total or av	20		3.4	

^aPVT-5 = preliminary variety trial-5, UVT-5 = uniform variety trial-5, UVT-6 = uniform variety trial-6. ^b*,** = significant at 5 and 1% level.